

NATIONAL FOOD OF THE KARAKALPAK PEOPLE

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Abstract. In this article the national cuisine of the Karakalpaks is discussed. It talks about the porridge, cereals, mashaba, and bilamik, which are prepared from cereals. National dishes such as sour cream, shubat, and irimshik made from milk, as well as fish soup, fish karma, and fried fish, are studied. The conditions for their preparation are investigated.

Keywords: cereals, porridge, mashaba, kuwirmash, maysok, types of takan, fried fish, fish soup, fish.

The centuries-old life and culture of the Karakalpak people are associated with their social and spiritual life, various customs, traditions and beliefs. The concepts about them are preserved in the vocabulary of Karakalpak language, which consists of ethnographic expressions. We can also see this in the example of the traditions of the people related to nutrition and the preparation of national dishes. Although food is common to all peoples of the world, there are national dishes that are characteristic of national ethnographic features. Therefore, studying ethnographic expressions related to the national dishes of the Karakalpaks helps to identify the national features of our people. This shows the importance of studying this topic.

In Karakalpak ethnography, food terms play an important role in highlighting the national identity of the people. K. Mambetov says about this: "Although Karakalpak cuisine does not have any special differences from the peoples of Central Asia, it has many unique characteristics" [9:90]. The food products and items used in the preparation of Karakalpak national dishes are similar to those of the Turkic peoples, some are almost the same. For example, K. Khojabayeva in her article mentioned that *ayran*, *bilamiq*, *bawirsaq*, *kespe*, *súzbe*, *sút* - these are used by both Turkmen and Karakalpak peoples [11:123].

The Karakalpak people have their own national dishes. Ethnographic expressions related to food in Karakalpak language are used, such as *gúrtik*, *kespas*, *máshgóje*, *júweri gúrtik*, *atalay*, *basalay*, *qatibilamiq*, *shorpa*, *mashaba*, *mashpalaw*, *tuwrama*, *qarma*, *aqsawlaq*. They are prepared from various types of food products: cereals, dairy products, meat, etc. According to this uniqueness, we will learn national dishes dividing them into the following groups according to the food products they are prepared from.

1. Dishes made from cereals. There are also several types and names of bread products in Karakalpak language. The first appeared bread among the Karakalpak and other Turkic peoples is *kómesh*. In M. Kashkari's work, the word "kómásh" is given in the meaning of "bread baked burying in ember in the oven" [3:415]. Among the local peoples, there are such types of bread as *taba nan*, *qatlama nan*, *zağara*, *pátir*, *nan jappay*, *góshnan*, *uwildırıq nan*, etc.

Yaqshı dosqa bergil *nanıw shórekiñ*... [1:130] Give a good friend a piece of bread...

Shaydı qoy, *pátirdi* qoy, qolıña ayrı, arqan al [1:163] Pour the tea, put the patir (flatbread), take a fork in your hand, take a rope.

Góje is one of the national dishes of the Karakalpak people. Many scientists consider grain to be the main of the food. Because grain is the first food cooked on fire. Its simplest type - *góje*

is considered one of the national dishes of our people. Firstly, the grain is crushed in *keli*, separated from the husk, cooked in water, and it becomes *góje* (porridge). In our people's ethnographies related to food names, the following terms for porridge are found: *júweri góje*, *tari góje*, *arpa góje*, *másh góje*, *lobiya góje*, *gúrish góje*, *Nawrız góje*, etc. Porridge is often cooked with milk, yogurt, suzma, and ayran. Depending on its variety, it can be cooked with mung bean, beans, and rice, and frying with oil. The saying «Jarasıǵı bolmaǵan jazı qurısın, asqatıǵı bolmaǵan ası qursın» is from this. For example:

Tań azannan hámmе atqa er qoyıp, From the morning, everyone mounted their horses,
Mázi asqatıqsız gójege toyıp. [2:161] being pleased and full of porridge.

This dish is known in Karakalpak language as *máshaba*. There is a saying among the people that «*máshaba másh keltirer, sıqpan ashtan óltirer*» (*mashaba* brings mung bean, and *sikhpan* kills with hunger).

Máshaba is a dish made by boiling mung bean in water, adding yogurt and frying with oil: Eki tabaq *máshabanı* dás soqtıń góy [7:292] (You have eaten two bowls of *mashaba*).

Jarma (Cereal) is one of the most famous national dishes of the Karakalpaks. If the grain is cracked in the mill, it turns into cereal. Cereal is most often made from sorghum. Milk, yogurt or ayran are also added to this dish: Diyqannıń úyine barsań *jarma* ishersen [8:66]. (If you go to a farmer's house, you will eat cereal).

After the grain is ground in a mill and turned into flour, from it several national dishes are prepared. The most famous of them is *bılamıq*.

Bılamıq is a dish prepared in a hurry. If you add flour to boiling water in a cauldron, it will cook like a thick soup. Then yogurt is added to it and served. If you put a lot of flour in a cauldron, it will thicken like porridge, and turn into *qatıbılamıq*. Then it is placed on a plate, poured with butter. This type of dish is a national dish of the Abkhaz people, which is considered a delicacy. In the folk saying, «*Ishkeniń bolsa bılamıq, basalayı taǵı bar*» ("If you have *bılamik*, then there is more," or in the literary works, we find this saying about it: Nabada kewili ashılıp jarlıqaǵan kúni báybishi bir sańruz un berse, qatırǵan menen bir gúlsheden artıq shıqpaytuǵın bolǵan soń ayrandı qaynatıp sol undı ishine salıp, qoyıwıraq *bılamıq* pisiredi [6:43] (On the day when the rich man's wife is in good and kind mood, she gave her a handful of flour, knowing it could be only a little Johnny-cake she would boil ayran, she would put flour in the pot and cook a thicker *bılamik*). A thick *bılamik* (*qatıbılamik*) is also considered a famous national dish of the Karakalpaks.

Quwirmash is one of the dishes that the Karakalpaks have eaten since ancient times. It is a dish made by frying rice, millet, corn, and other grains in a pot: "Há, apa, kóp sózdi qoy, balańa az ǵana *quwirmash* ber,– dedi [8:264]. (Hey, mother, stop talking so much, give your child a little *kuwirmash*," [8:264].

Sók is a grain obtained by boiling millet, roasting it, and removing the bran. Karakalpaks cooked more national dishes from the millet. *Sók* was prepared by boiling millet. Its butter-soaked form *maysók* was given to women and girls as a gift when a child was born.

Qız anası keler besik arqalap, The mother of the girl came carrying a cradle,
Miywe-shiywe, bawırsaq, *maysók* dorbalap, taking fruits, boursak, maisuk,
Bárshe aǵayınler kelse jorbalap, All the relatives came gathered,
Qáde-qáwmetlerge tolǵan besik toy [10:50]. Besik tuy full of traditions [10:50].

S. Kamalov focused on the Karakalpaks' occupation of agriculture and the *sók góje*, *maysók* which are prepared from millet, and showed that they were prepared not as complexly as plov

[5:94]. Sok was also drunk by adding it to yogurt. They boiled it in milk and made porridge. They made *takan* from the *sok*.

Taqan is made from plant grains grounded into flour. It is used as a soft food. In Karakalpaks, depending on the plant from which *takan* is made, there are types of *takan*: *sók taqan*, *júweri taqan*, and *jiyde taqan*. S. Kamalov noted that *jiyde* (*Elaeagnus*) was used in ancient times as a substitute for sugar and spices, and that from it *jiyde taqan* (*Elaeagnus takan*) was often prepared as a special dish [5:99].

2. Dairy dishes. Milk dishes have been of great importance in the life of the people and have been used as food and for the treatment of diseases since ancient times. For example:

Kimdi ayırar *maydan*, kimdi *toraqtan*... Who will be separated in the field, who from *torak*...

Jegip kúshin, *sútin* sawıp ishpeséñ... [1:162] If you win the strength, not drinking milk...
Ishpege *ayran*, jemege nan bolmasa, If there is no *ayran* to drink, and no bread to eat,

Hawa anadan qalğan jol, neter deyseñ... [1:183] the path left by *Eva*, what will you say...

Qaymaq (Cream) is a thick layer on the surface of raw, cooked milk or other liquids. *Qaymaq* is a Turkic word. The word *qaymaq* is found in the form of *shyak* in Old Turkic written records. In modern Turkic languages, there are variants in the form of *qaymaq* in Karakalpak, Kazakh; in Uzbek *qaymoq*; in Turkmen *gaymak*; in Azerbaijani *gaymag*; in Kumyk *kaymak*.

Shubat is a fermented drink made from camel milk. When various drinks are used from yogurt, the fat of that drink is removed on the side. It is called *sarı may*, *siyirdiñ mayı* (butter, cow's fat).

Sarı may (Butter) is used in phonetic variants in Turkic languages: in Uzbek, *sori moy*// *sori ëğ*; *sarı may* in Kazakh; *eğ* in Azerbaijani; in Turkmen *mesge yağ*// *sarı yağ*.

Irimshik is a dish prepared by boiling fermented milk, putting it in a curd bag and drying it in the sun. In modern Turkic languages, it is found in the following form: in Azerbaijani *ağız*; in Kazakh *uız*; in Kyrgyz *uuz*; in Kumyk *uvuz*; in Tatar *ugız*; in Uzbek *oğiz sūt*.

Súzbe (Curd) is made from yogurt, milk and other dairy products.

3. Fish meals. The Karakalpaks lived at the end of the Amudarya River, on the shores of the Aral Sea, and in the lakes there was an abundance of carp, barbell, sheat-fish, pike-perch, pike and white breams. They boiled them in water, drank their soup, and ate their meat. The Karakalpaks cherish fish as the food of their ancestors. In this regard, S. Kamalov's work states that fish dishes were a favorite food of the people [5:107].

Fishing is a widely developed field among the Karakalpaks. In the Karakalpak language, there are many types of dishes made from fish, such as *balıq sorpa* (fish soup), *balıq qarma* (fish karma), *balıq quwirdaq* (fried fish), as well as *balıq kotlet*, *jarkop* (fish cutlets and roast), which came from the traditions of Western countries. Fish soup and karma are considered part of the daily meal of the people.

Qarma (Karma) is a type of dish made from fish. It is made by leaving a little soup, removing the bones, adding finely small *gúrtik* (rolled out and cut into small pieces of dough), and then stirring and cooking. In Karakalpak language, karma has two meanings: 1) after cooking fish, the bones are removed, and soup is mixed with the sorghum flour and karma is ready; 2) cooked rice without meat. The fish is cleaned, threaded on a tamarisk stick, placed on a fire, sprinkled with seraph, and made into a kebab. It is fried. It is sprinkled with a little oil, placed on a pan, and fried.

Recently, cutlets have begun to be made from fish. Previously, *taba nan* was made from fish roe. Now it has become a tradition to salt it, spread it on bread and eat. The Uzbek folk poet Mirtemir writes in his collection of poems called «Qaraqalpaq dápteri» (“Notebook of Karakalpak”) as follows:

Shetirek jaylasqan kishkene bólme, A small room located on a far side,
Aldına jayılgan hár túr balıqlar, All kinds of fish spread out in front,
Balıq sorpa dástúr bul ázim elge, Fish soup is a tradition in this great country,
Kimge balıq kerek, kelip qalıńlar. Whoever needs fish, come and take.

That is why fish is valued in this country equally with mutton. For these reasons, among the people there are such sayings as «Bekireniń bel kespesin jemegen sorlı basım, qoydıń quyqalı góshine tap boldım» (“My poor head that has not eaten the sturgeon meat, I have come across the meat of a sheep with bones”) and «Shortanıń zor bolǵanda Xiywaǵa barmas pa edi?» (“If the pike was big, wouldn’t he have gone to Khiva?”)

In short, in the past our ancestors prepared national dishes from cereals, dairy products, cattle, poultry and fish meat. Even today, these national dishes and their names are still used quite often. Such national food names, which are used in the ethnographic vocabulary of Karakalpak language, provide valuable information about the socio-economic life and livelihood of the people.

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